

Pathways to Interdisciplinary and Transdisciplinary Research: the SHAPE-ID Toolkit

Find tools and resources to make informed decisions about interdisciplinary and transdisciplinary research with the Arts, Humanities and Social Sciences, the Sciences, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics, and societal partners.

Top Ten Tips Collection

on Inter- and Transdisciplinary Research

Abstract

SHAPE-ID partners have drawn upon their experience of inter- and transdisciplinary research to provide their top ten practical tips that offer our distilled wisdom on seven key tasks regarding inter- and transdisciplinary research, namely writing a research proposal, multi-stakeholder collaborations, working with policymakers, evaluating research, research funding programmes, developing a career and mentoring.

Compiled by

Isabel Fletcher, Catherine Lyall, Christian Pohl

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SHAPE-ID consortium members

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This publication is an extract of the SHAPE-ID Toolkit. For a general overview, visit: [10.5281/zenodo.4743703](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4743703).

The Toolkit provides tools and resources to make informed decisions about interdisciplinary and transdisciplinary research with the Arts, Humanities and Social Sciences, the Sciences, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics, and societal partners.

Contributors & Co-producers

The Top Ten Tips collection is based on discussions with and inputs from the SHAPE-ID consortium members, namely Anna Buchner, Maureen Burgess, Bianca Vienni Baptista, Caitriona Curtis, Isabel Fletcher, Giorgia Galvini, Catherine Lyall, Maciej Maryl, Jane Ohlmeyer, Christian Pohl, Andrea Ricci, Carlo Sessa, Jack Spaapen, Sibylle Studer, Doireann Wallace, Piotr Wciślik, Keisha Taylor Wesselink, Declan Whelan-Curtin.

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Top Ten Tips for writing inter- and transdisciplinary research proposals **from SHAPE-ID partner, [Dr Isabel Fletcher](#)**

1

Remember your proposal will be read by a range of people, not just those within your research area: don't assume knowledge of your discipline – describe (concisely) why your research is important, innovative, impactful etc.

2

Don't just describe your proposal as interdisciplinary or transdisciplinary. Explain why an inter- or transdisciplinary approach is necessary to achieve the intended research outcomes.

3

Inter- and trans-disciplinary proposals may be evaluated by those with expertise in collaborative research rather than your discipline. Write clearly for a general reader – use the minimum of technical language and abbreviations and define specialist terms briefly when they are first used.

4

Collaboration and integration take many forms and work to achieve. Outline what kind(s) of collaboration/integration you envisage (theoretical, methodological, etc.) and the specific ways in which you hope to achieve this.

5

Explain the methods that you plan to use and, if they are novel, give examples where they have been successfully used in other fields.

6

Bear in mind the extra costs associated with inter- or transdisciplinary research (such as, for example, additional network building), and budget for them accordingly.

7

If the research involves new collaborations, assume that these relationships will take time to develop and provide opportunities (formal and informal) for this to happen, especially at the start of the project.

8

If the research includes non-academic partners describe what they bring to the research, what and when they are expected to contribute, and how they will benefit from taking part.

9

Plan for a range of outputs to be produced across the lifetime of the project – this protects against failure and satisfies the needs of different collaborators. Academic publications are usually of little importance to societal partners who will often need more focused outputs – a programme of activities or new tool to pilot – in order to justify their continued involvement in the project.

10

Criteria for authorship vary considerably across disciplines. Describe how authorships for project outputs will be allocated - or a process for agreeing on this early in the project - otherwise this can become a major problem.

Further Resources

- SHAPE-ID toolkit: [Creating Collaborative Conditions](#)

About the Author

Dr Isabel Fletcher is a qualitative social scientist whose research is based in science and technology studies, but also incorporates approaches from sociology, food policy and public health policy. She has research interests in UK and European policy approaches to food, nutrition and eating, and the ways in which interdisciplinary research is used to address complex social problems. Isabel has worked in a variety of interdisciplinary contexts on a wide range of topics including public health models of obesity, food security policy, and sustainable diets.

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Top Ten Tips for working in multi-stakeholder collaborations **from SHAPE-ID partner, [Dr Christian Pohl](#)**

1

In principle, try to assemble the stakeholders so that they include the full range of perspectives on the issue. Be aware, when doing so, that you will have to discuss the normative orientation of the project (what do we mean by, e.g. improved health, equality, sustainable development). However, this will not work if some stakeholders have immutable positions.

2

In principle, let each stakeholder group decide who they send to represent their group. Deviate from this principle if this form of representation is part of the problem or not possible.

3

Don't have all meetings at your own offices or institution. Ask stakeholders if they would like to host meetings too.

4

Inter- and transdisciplinary project have an evolving character, and the main topic can change over time. As a consequence, some stakeholders lose interest and others may be needed as the project evolves. If major shifts in the topic happen, address the question of who is no longer interested and wants to step out and who is missing and should be included.

5

Early in the project, collect the stakeholders' expectations (including yours) for the project. Sort these expectations into those that seem achievable and those that will be beyond the scope of the project. Share and discuss the sorted expectations with the stakeholders.

6

Don't assume that all stakeholders have to be involved all the time. Clarify the role and expertise of each stakeholder in the project and ask yourself: When in the project must they be involved and in what form?

7

Be aware that some stakeholders can't participate in inter- and transdisciplinary research in their worktime/as part of their job, and others can. Clarify what applies to whom. Think about compensations for those who need it. Also, small/symbolic compensations are usually much appreciated.

8

Be aware that some stakeholders do not join just because of your project, but also to network and discuss issues with the other stakeholders. Offer enough time for informal meetings and networking among the stakeholders.

9

Not all stakeholders participate in the academic culture of sharing results and open discussion. Some of them can't because of property rights and competition. Check early in the project whether this is the case and prepare an agreement clarifying property rights and confidentiality of interim results and discussions if need.

10

Explore methods and tools to co-produce knowledge with the stakeholders. An explorative setting can help to challenge established routines and hierarchies.

Further Resources

🔗 SHAPE-ID toolkit: [Co-create a research project](#)

About the Author

Dr Christian Pohl is Co-Director of the Transdisciplinarity Lab of the Department of Environmental Systems Science (TdLab) at ETH Zurich with a habilitation at the University of Bern. He has been studying inter- and transdisciplinary research since the late 1990s and recently developed a toolbox for co-producing knowledge.

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Top Ten Tips for working with policymakers from **SHAPE-ID** partner, [Professor Catherine Lyall](#)

1

It is generally recognised that the impact of academic research on policy is often long-term and indirect.

2

Getting knowledge into policy requires a willingness to engage with different audiences who may have quite different agendas and timescales from those of the academic researcher. It also requires research outputs in a different format and language from traditional academic publications.

3

Policy-relevant evidence is contestable and open to interpretation – policy is necessarily political.

4

Policymakers work with multiple and shifting political agendas, often with short timeframes for action, factors which have a significant influence on their engagement with research findings.

5

Policymakers may need short, sharp, timely pieces of work; a good policy message which comes along after a decision has been taken will rarely have influence.

6

Increasing the impact of research on policy and practice demands more than just post-hoc dissemination. It should aim to achieve dialogue with potential research users at the earliest possible stage, potentially involving them in agenda-setting and in the design process.

7

Many people and organisations are involved in translating evidence for policy. Identify key “knowledge intermediaries” who may help to get your message across. These may be other societal actors who are partners in your transdisciplinary research.

8

The key elements of an effective policy brief are:

- A summary and a list of key points up front
- A clear structure with well signposted sections
- Use of boxes for figures, case-studies, glossaries and other contextual materials
- Accessible jargon free language

9

Publicise your policy briefing through social media channels, research and professional networks, etc.

10

Consider professional media training to improve your communication skills.

Further Resources

➔ SHAPE-ID toolkit: [Disseminate Research Findings](#)

About the Author

Prof Catherine Lyall is author of [Being an Interdisciplinary Academic. How Institutions Shape University Careers](#) and co-author of [Interdisciplinary Research Journeys. Practical Strategies for Capturing Creativity](#)

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Top Ten Tips for evaluating inter- and transdisciplinary research **from SHAPE-ID partners, [Dr Christian Pohl](#) and [Dr Isabel Fletcher](#)**

1

Accept that interdisciplinary and transdisciplinary (ID/TD) evaluation processes may be different from those in other research areas, and include evaluators with different kinds of expertise, including expertise in inter- and transdisciplinary research. This will require combining rigour with flexibility, pragmatism and perhaps patience.

2

Make sure there are a range of quality criteria concerning the goals that should be achieved by inter- and transdisciplinary research (integration of perspectives, comprehensive view, impact beyond science) – these should have been agreed in advance, and in some cases include an indication of how they will differ from the criteria applied to conventional research.

3

Be open minded about other approaches to research, and to other understandings of inter and transdisciplinarity. Be aware of your own inevitable biases – probably acquired from your training and experience – and prepared to discuss disagreements constructively.

4

To avoid opportunistic labelling of research as inter- or transdisciplinary (e.g. in response to a funding call), you need to critically assess the arguments demonstrating that these research questions demand ID/TD approaches and methods.

5

Equally important are considerations of project feasibility and implementation: are/were the proposed methods and processes feasible and can they be/have they been implemented properly? Do the proposed methods and processes indicate the applicants' familiarity with inter- and transdisciplinary research?

6

Evaluate proposals according to how they plan to achieve/have achieved objectives: what resources are allocated; what disciplines are included; are these adequate disciplines to achieve the objectives? Is there a sound and realistic plan on how to work together? Are there methods and tools for integration?

7

Relationships with partners (academic and societal) take a considerable amount of time to develop and good communication is critical: are /were enough resources (finances, time, methods and tools) allocated to developing these relationships?

8

Evaluators need to take into account that – due of the complexity of the problem studied and/or the co-production methods used – ID and TD research can contain more unknowns than other type of research. Evaluation may, therefore, need to focus on the quality of research processes rather than specific outcomes.

9

The outputs of inter- and transdisciplinary research are often more diverse than those of more conventional research and may happen at all moments of exchange between participants. This may require the use of different indicators and metrics to both capture all outputs and assess their quality, again also taking the process into account.

10

Impact should include not just short-term tangible effects (new jobs, additional turnover, product improvements, etc.), but also long-term structural effects which are more linked to ID and TD research practice, such as training, community building, disruptive ideas and social innovation.

Further Resources

🔗 SHAPE-ID toolkit: [Evaluate inter- and transdisciplinary research](#)

About the Authors

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Top Ten Tips for developing inter- and transdisciplinary research funding programmes from **SHAPE-ID partner**, [Professor Catherine Lyall](#)

1

Successful programmes take deliberate steps throughout to achieve integration and coherence. Additional small-scale funding for network- and community-building in the early stages of a research initiative contributes greatly to the degree and extent of integration.

2

The language used in a funding call is important: inclusive, accessible and jargon-free language can open up a topic in a way that invites different perspectives and encourages projects that challenge prevailing approaches.

3

Consider which level(s) are to be the chief platform for inter- or transdisciplinarity: at programme level (for larger-scale initiatives); at theme level (i.e. a sub-programme level) where certain topics might be integrated across projects; or at project level, within a project team or individual project members.

4

Who will provide the necessary inter- or transdisciplinary leadership: the funders, the academic Programme Director or a team of individuals in charge of component projects? How will external advisory boards be used to best effect?

5

When selecting leaders for inter- or transdisciplinary research programmes, leadership skills and integrative vision may need to be weighted more heavily than a conventional academic track record within a single discipline.

6

A great deal of tacit knowledge about the management of inter- or transdisciplinary research programmes can be held by funding agency staff: how will this people-embodied knowledge be captured to ensure continuity if key staff leave?

7

Capacity building—the development of knowledge and strengthening of skills, competencies and abilities of people, networks and the research community—is critical to the growth and longevity of inter- and transdisciplinary research. As well as supporting such activities, funders should recognise that the Arts and Humanities often have less experience in co-creation and collaborative research and so may require additional support to improve their readiness to participate in and lead such research.

8

Ensure that learning from past experiences of inter- and transdisciplinary investments becomes embedded within collective organisational memory. This requires greater continuity of research networks and communities, and also of research careers so that future career options are available for inter- and transdisciplinary early-career researchers and their expertise is not lost at the end of a programme.

9

Incorporating flexibility into a programme's budget allows not only evolution but also an opportunity for research leaders to develop new ways to facilitate genuine inter- and transdisciplinarity and encourage organisational and cross-institutional learning.

10

Inter- and transdisciplinary capacity-building is a long-term process: in understanding the needs of societal partners, funders need to recognise that negotiating and co-producing knowledge collaboratively can require more time to achieve the genuine integration and mutual understanding needed to solve a problem effectively.

Further Resources

- SHAPE-ID toolkit: [Top Ten Tips for Evaluation](#)
- SHAPE-ID toolkit: [Fund Collaborative Research Projects](#)

About the Author

Prof Catherine Lyall is author of [Being an Interdisciplinary Academic. How Institutions Shape University Careers](#) and co-author of [Interdisciplinary Research Journeys. Practical Strategies for Capturing Creativity](#)

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Top Ten Tips for inter- and transdisciplinary academic careers **from SHAPE-ID partner, [Professor Catherine Lyall](#)**

1

Especially if you are an early stage researcher, recognise that drawing on and integrating two or more bodies of literature, methodologies and research cultures will be challenging – don't be too hard on yourself and don't be afraid of asking for help.

2

It is easy to feel isolated, unless based with like-minded individuals, so try to find people to share problems and lessons learned with – think about networking and community building within and beyond your institution.

3

Build core competencies to sustain inter- and transdisciplinary research careers. These include “metaskills” training (such as leadership, communication, negotiation, etc.) and general “academic life skills” – a good mentor can help with these.

4

If you are studying for a PhD, use your supervisors to help you set manageable boundaries and work with your supervisors to ensure clarity and continuity of communication between all parties about methodologies, format and the focus of your thesis

5

Labels seem to matter in academia so think carefully about your “academic identity”: how do you present yourself and your research to others? This may vary depending on your audience and can also evolve over time.

6

Spell out what is your unique contribution - it may not be obvious to someone from another discipline. Interdisciplinary projects may not provide new knowledge within a discipline but from the intersection of several disciplines.

7

You may need to be more strategic to secure career advancement in comparison with your mono-disciplinary peers: plan your portfolio of publications and conference presentations

8

Annotate your CV to explain your contributions to collaborative work

9

Talk to your institutional leaders and call them to account if the institutional rhetoric about valuing inter- and transdisciplinary is hindered by academic and administrative structures.

10

Contribute to your community - knowledge of the benefits of inter-and transdisciplinary research and their contribution to academic careers will grow when its practitioners participate in peer review, the development of new funding schemes and mentoring.

Further Resources

🔗 SHAPE-ID toolkit: [Develop a career in inter-and transdisciplinary research](#)

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Top Ten Tips for mentoring academic careers in inter- and transdisciplinary research **from SHAPE-ID partners,** [Professor Catherine Lyall and Dr Isabel Fletcher](#)

1

Early career ID/TD researchers need to be even more strategic to secure career advancement in comparison with their mono-disciplinary peers. Be realistic about the current challenges of establishing an ID/TD career and help them to plan a portfolio of publications, research proposals, etc. In some countries, there is a gradual move towards broader assessment criteria, evidenced in more narrative forms of CV/resume that might be especially beneficial for ID/TD scholars.

2

Recognise that the situation may have changed since you were at the beginning of your career, particularly if you have been in permanent employment for a while.

3

If you offer to mentor someone, be professional in your interactions: be honest about your availability, try to stick to agreed meeting times and any deadlines for feedback. Also be open about the extent of your own commitment to an ID/TD approach; try to avoid pushing mentees towards any school or field that you, yourself, might embrace.

4

Labels seem to matter in academia so encourage your mentee to think about their “academic identity”; how they present themselves and their research and whether this may change over time or vary depending on their audience. As a mentor, it is not your role to create a “mini-me” but to encourage the growth and development of the mentee’s own identity.

5

It is easy to feel isolated, unless based with like-minded individuals, so help your mentee to develop networking and community building within and beyond their institution.

6

Encourage the building of core competencies to sustain inter- and transdisciplinary research careers. These include “metaskills” training (such as leadership, communication, negotiation, etc.) and general “academic life skills”. Remember that tacit knowledge about how institutions operate is difficult to acquire and valuable.

7

Encourage early career colleagues to contribute to your community - knowledge of the benefits of inter- and transdisciplinary research and their contribution to academic careers will grow when its practitioners participate in peer review, the development of new funding schemes and mentoring.

8

Mentoring can take many forms, depending on the individuals and their roles, and so your mentee may have a group of mentors – both formal and informal – who provide them with different kinds of advice and support.

Remember that not all issues require action, sometimes talking through a difficult situation is sufficient.

9

Talk to your institutional leaders and call them to account if the institutional rhetoric about valuing inter- and transdisciplinary is hindered by academic and administrative structures.

10

If possible, when mentoring those on fixed-term contracts, be prepared to continue the relationship beyond the end of your formal responsibilities. It is much harder to establish a career without this kind of ongoing support.

Further Resources

- SHAPE-ID toolkit: [Develop a career in inter-and transdisciplinary research](#)
- Dr Kirsi Cheas, who helped us to produce this document, is developing the Global Mentorship Initiative with the goals of 1) extending access to sustainable and context-sensitive mentoring and peer-support for ID-TD early-career researchers and students in different parts of the globe and especially in the Global South and 2) increasing awareness about the specific challenges and forms of discrimination experienced by ID-TD early-careers in different regional and other contexts. More information about this initiative can be found here: https://drive.google.com/file/d/1K73UbpGq_P-Po9yR-o_Y8hKdrcOu2jkS/view?usp=sharing

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